

THEORETICAL ISSUES OF POTTERY TERMINOLOGY IN TAJIK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract:

The article investigates theoretical issues of terminology, history of study and opinions of scholars in this field, sources of formation of pottery terms in Tajik and English languages, etymological analysis of some pottery terms, thematic classification of terms.

Key words: pottery terms, terminology, linguistics, a word, a phrase.

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Term and its explanation in linguistic sources provides information about the origin of the theory of term and terminology, its development and study in linguistics, as well as analyzes and reviews the opinions and research results of linguists on this problem. A term occupies a special place in the lexical composition of each language and differs from other linguistic units by some distinctive functional, lexico-semantic, morphological and stylistic-nominative features. One of the characteristic features of a term is its structural organization. As a result of continuous development of science and technology in the conditions of globalization, each specific branch has its own terminology. Each term is an element of language, which has a specific scientific essence and with its special features is easily distinguished from commonly used words [1; 18].

In our opinion, a term is a word and a phrase combination related only to one sphere, and its difference from commonly used words is manifested only in the context of a sentence or a branch text. Like a word, it is capable of having multiple meanings and synonymy, as well as homonymy.

Basic concepts of pottery terminology in scientific and historical sources interprets the issues of formation and evolution of pottery terms. Since its inception, mankind has dealt with clay and soil and people have made various products necessary for life from them [4; 78]. Pottery shards, pottery are found wherever excavations are conducted and countless studies have been published on the nature of pottery in a particular historical monument by scientists, archaeologists, art historians, chemists, and representatives of various fields of science [3; 85].

If we consider the history of the origin of pottery terms, the vocabulary and terms of that period can be classified into two main periods:

1. Terms and term combinations of the hand pottery period. The origin story of this period is still unclear and there is debate among historians about its terminology. Basically, pottery activities of this period were carried out by hand and consisted of the following terms and term combinations: gil - clay, zarf - vessel; mahsuloti safoli - earthenware, ware; ko'ra - kiln; safolgari - pottery; charkhi kuloli - potter's wheel (clay, ware, pottery, kiln,

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pottery, potter's wheel). Most of the terms mentioned are used in the form of term combinations.

2. Terms and term combinations referring to the period of the use of the potter's wheel. According to historians, mankind invented the potter's wheel 3500 years B.C., and with it was born a new era in the technology of clay processing and pottery making. Different countries around the world still make products using the potter's wheel. The vocabulary and terms that were popular during this period are kulol, humdon, tano'rsozi, kuloli dasti, hok, mahsuloti kuloli, hoki kulol, hokkanak. If we look at the morphological structure of the named terms, most of them are used today in the form of word combinations created by means of syntactic connection.

Sources of formation of pottery terms of Tajik and English languages analyzes those sources that occupy a special place in the formation and development of pottery terms of Tajik and English languages. The role of historical-geographical, scientific and artistic works, as well as dictionaries is very great in the formation and development of pottery terms, and the most popular of them are: "Tojikon" (Tajiks) [Gafurov, 2020], "Pictorial Archaeological Dictionary" [Savvonidi, 1995], "Pottery of Central Asia" [Peshchevereva, 1959], "Ceramics of Tajikistan" [Peschevereva, 1959], "Ceramics of Tajikistan" [Odinaev, 2018], etc.

Etymological analysis of some key pottery terms in the compared languages, in which some key pottery words and terms are analyzed in terms of etymology. In this section, the terms: gil, kulol, k̄yza, d̄ylcha, k̄yra, pot, potter, clay, cup, kiln (clay, potter, jug, scoop, kiln) were compared in terms of their etymological features. From the etymological analysis of the above mentioned English terms it became known that they originate from Latin (cup, kiln, base, flux); Greek (beaker); German (clay, bowl, wheel, slip, ware, fettle, fire, quill, rib, sand, wire); French (pot, soil, plate, vase, cover, pitcher, bat, enamel, cone, flamble, lustre, lute, mold, pintch, porcelain, bique); French (pot, soil, plate, vase, cover, pitcher, bat, enamel, cone, flamble, lustre, lute, mold, pintch, porcelain, bique); Danish (dish, spoute, flint) and Italian, and today form part of the vocabulary of English.

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